

FEED EFFICIENCY AND INTAKE IN PRATAP DHAN CHICKENS UNDER PHYTASE SUPPLEMENTATION AND VARYING ENERGY DIETS

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ABSTRACT	KEYWORDS
The present study was conducted to evaluate the Effect of phytase enzyme supplementation at varying dietary energy levels on the feed intake and feed conversion ratio of Pratapdhan chickens (day-old). They were used in a completely randomized design in 5 treatments with 4 replicates, each consisting of 10 chicks.	Phytase, supplementation, enzyme, pratapdhan, feed intake, FCR (Feed Conversion Ratio)

Introduction

Pratap Dhan has emerged as a promising dual-purpose bird developed under the All India Coordinated Research Project (AICRP) on Poultry Breeding at MPUAT, Udaipur, and Rajasthan. This variety closely resembles local indigenous birds and is well-suited to rural and backyard farming systems. Modern hybrid layer birds now produce an average of 310-320 eggs per year, a significant improvement from the 240-250 eggs produced three decades ago. Similarly, present-day broilers achieve a marketable body weight of 1.8 to 2.0 kg in just 38 days, with a feed conversion ratio (FCR) of 1.6 to 1.8. Chicken meat is not only a rich source of high-quality protein and essential nutrients but also relatively low in fat especially when the skin is removed. It is versatile in meal planning, easy to prepare, and widely available in various forms, including raw, pre-packaged and ready-to-eat options (Shedeed, 1999) ^[1]. Furthermore, chicken meat contains a higher proportion of unsaturated fatty acids and lower cholesterol, making it a healthy dietary choice suitable for people of all age groups.

Phytase, a naturally occurring enzyme, catalyzes the hydrolysis of phytate (inositol hexakisphosphate), thereby enhancing phosphorus availability in poultry diets. According to Ravindran *et al.* (1999) ^[2], phytic acid contains approximately 28.2% phosphorus, yet its bioavailability to poultry is extremely low. Therefore, the present research was undertaken to investigate the effect of dietary supplementation of phytase at varying levels of metabolizable energy on the feed intake and food conversion ratio of Pratap Dhan chicken.

Materials and Methods

Two-hundred-day old straight run Pratapdhan chicks were procured from AICRP on poultry Breeding, Rajasthan College of Agriculture, Udaipur and randomly divided into 5 dietary treatment groups with 4 replicates of 10 birds each. They were reared under deep litter system of housing as per standard rearing practices. They were used in a completely randomized design in 5 treatments with 4 replicates, each consisting of 10 chicks. The treatment comprised of T₁ Control basal diet (CP 20% and ME 2800 kcal/kg), T₂ Control ~ 1 ~ the mean values of feed intake during first week was 60.78±0.54, 59.47±1.18, 58±1.67, 65.1±1.34 and 65.32±1.57 in T₁, T₂, T₃,

T₄ and T₅, respectively. T₄ and T₅ recorded significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher feed consumption compared to T₁, T₂ and T₃. The reduction of energy in T₄ and T₅ resulted in more feed to compensate for a less efficient energy utilization in the early growth phase. By the second week, the mean value of feed intake was 117.17±1.77, 118.98±0.94, 112.79±2.84, 121.07±2.05 and 124.71±1.99 in T₁, T₂, T₃, T₄ and T₅, respectively and the trend of increased intake continued, with the highest values observed in T₅ and T₄. T₃ again exhibited relatively lower intake, possibly reflecting improved nutrient digestibility and feed efficiency under this treatment. During the third week, the mean value of feed intake was 226.37±1.71, 230.1±1.24, 234.12±1.00, 229.34±1.26 and 242.66±1.13 in T₁, T₂, T₃, T₄ and T₅, respectively.

Significantly ($p < 0.05$) highest feed intake was recorded in T₅ followed by T₃ and lowest in T₂, T₄ and T₁, however the feed intake in T₂, T₄ and T₁ remained statistically nonsignificant. In the fourth and fifth weeks, the mean value of feed intake of respective treatments in fourth and fifth week were 280.04±1.15, 288.37±1.75, 265.95±1.87, 283.09±1.81 and 294.97±1.86 and 353.79±0.63, 377.53±0.69,

381.52±1.18, 369.72±1.15 and 368.92±0.59 in T₁, T₂, and T₃, T₄ and T₅, respectively and feed intake continued to be significantly influenced by the treatment. T₅ showed the highest feed intake in fourth week and fifth week the feed intake was highest in T₃. The feed intake was lowest in T₃ and T₁ at fourth and fifth weeks respectively. Notably, during the sixth and seventh weeks, the mean value of feed intake in sixth and seventh weeks were 401.26±1.39, 422.42±1.27, 426.05±1.55, 378.95±1.12, 410.31±0.63 and 381.22±0.302, 419.38±0.87, 409.65±0.25, 379.52±1.98 and 409.62±3.10 in T₁, T₂, T₃, T₄ and T₅, respectively. The feed intake was significantly ($p < 0.05$) highest in T₃ and T₂ at 6th and 7th weeks respectively. The birds in T₄ recorded lowest feed diet (CP 20% and ME 2800 kcal/kg) + supplemented with Phytase @ 1500 FTU/Kg, T₃ (T₂ containing CP 20% and 2668 kcal/kg (5% reduction in ME)), T₄ (T₂ containing CP 20% and ME 2520 kcal/kg (10% reduction in ME)) and T₅ (T₂ containing CP 20% and ME 2380 kcal/kg (15% reduction in ME)). The observations recorded during the experiment will be statistically analysed by using standard procedure for analysis of variance of CRD (Completely Randomized Design) as suggested by Snedecor and Cochran (1994) [3].

(A) Weekly feed intake: The weekly feed intake was measured in each treatment group for the experimental period. Total feed offered and residue thereof was weighed to calculate feed intake.

Feed intake (g) = Feed offered during the current day (g) - Feed leftover at the next day (g) Total weekly feed intake was calculated by adding the daily feed intake for the said week.

(B) Feed conversion ratio (FCR) Feed conversion ratio was estimated at weekly interval as well as for the entire growth period upto 8 weeks of age. Feed conversion ratio was calculated by using following formula. Results and Discussion statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$) in feed Weekly feed intake consumption at each week of the experimental period, The weekly feed intake per bird across different treatment influenced by the phytase supplementation at different groups is depicted in Table 4.1. The data revealed dietary energy levels.

Table 4.1: Effect of supplementing phytase on Weekly Feed Intake (g/chick/week) in Pratapdhan chicks

Particulars	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5	SEm±	CD
1	60.78b±0.54	59.47b±1.18	58.32b±1.67	65.10a±1.34	65.32a±1.57	1.313	*3.993
2	117.17b±1.77	118.98a±0.94	112.79b±2.84	121.07a±2.05	124.71a±1.99	2.016	*6.133
3	226.37c±1.71	230.10c±1.24	234.12b±1.00	229.34c±1.26	242.66a±1.13	1.294	*3.937
4	280.04c±1.15	288.37b±1.75	265.95d±1.87	283.09c±1.81	294.97a±1.86	1.716	*5.218
5	353.79d±0.63	377.53b±0.69	381.52a±1.18	369.72c±1.15	368.92c±0.59	0.892	*2.713
6	401.26c±1.39	422.42a±1.27	426.05a±1.55	378.95d±1.12	410.31b±0.63	1.237	*3.763

7	381.22c±0.30	419.38a±0.87	409.65b±0.25	379.52c±1.98	409.62b±3.10	1.704	*5.182
8	506.26d±2.30	531.74b±1.38	551.66a±1.59	514.99c±1.12	526.66b±2.13	1.78	*5.414
Overall	2326.88c±4.14		2447.99a±4.10		2439.72a±3.58		2341.17b±5.09

2443.17a±4.77 4.418 *13.438 intake at both 6th and 7th weeks of age. The feed intake was reduced when the energy content was reduced to 10% of the requirement which may be attributed to higher nutrient demand with the advancement of the age. In the eighth week, the mean value of feed intake was 506.26±2.30, 531.74±1.38, 551.66±1.59, 514.99±1.12 and 526.66±2.13 in T₁, T₂, T₃, T₄ and T₅, respectively. The feed intake at 8th week was significantly ($p<0.05$) highest in T₃ followed by T₂ and T₅, T₄ and lowest in T₁. However, the difference of feed intake in T₂ and T₅ was found to be statistically non-significant (1.12 g) recorded relatively lower values. The mean values for total feed intake up to 8week experimental period were 2326.88±4.14, 2447.99±4.10, 2439.72±3.58, 2341.17±5.09 and

2443.17±4.77 g in T₁, T₂, T₃, T₄ and T₅, respectively. The total feed intake was significantly ($p<0.05$) higher in T₂, T₅ and T₃ followed by T₄ and lowest in T₁. However, difference in feed intake amongst T₂, T₃ and T₅ was small and statistically non-significant.

Feed conversion ratio (FCR)

Chicks is presented in Table 4.2. FCR is a critical indicator of production efficiency, with a lower value representing better feed utilization. In the first week, the mean values of FCR were 4.65±0.42, 4.72±0.35, 3.48±0.29, 3.84±0.17 and 4.34±0.09 in T₁, T₂, T₃, T₄ and T₅, respectively whereas, FCR values varied significantly ($p<0.05$). The T₃ group demonstrated significantly superior feed efficiency compared to all other groups, indicating better nutrient assimilation and growth response to phytase at this level. T₄ also showed a relatively lower FCR, whereas T₁, T₂ and T₅ recorded higher FCRs, reflecting comparatively less efficient feed utilization. By the second week, the mean value of FCR were 2.61±1.17, 2.53±0.09, 2.15±0.05, 3.68±0.09 and 3.16±0.14 in T₁, T₂, T₃, T₄ and T₅, respectively whereas, the lowest FCR was observed in T₃, followed by T₂ and T₁, with the highest values recorded in T₅ and T₄. The difference in FCR between T₁ and T₂ was found to be non-significant. These results indicated higher feed efficiency in during the early growth phase. In the third week, the mean value of FCR were 2.82±0.03, 3.06±0.06, 2.80±0.03, 2.95±0.03 and 2.93±0.04 in T₁, T₂, T₃, T₄ and T₅, respectively. The FCR was significantly higher in T₂, T₄ and T₅ as compared to T₁ and T₃. The FCR in T₂, T₄ and T₅ was similar and FCR in T₁ and T₃ were also at par. However, T₂, T₄ and T₅ recorded significantly poorer FCR values, suggesting the feed efficiency could not be sustained beyond 5% reduction in energy content in the feed.

Table 4.2: Effect of supplementing phytase on weekly feed conversion ratio (FCR) in Pratapdhan chicks

Age (Weeks)	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5	SEm±	CD
1	4.65a±0.42	4.72a±0.35	3.48b±0.29	3.84b±0.17	4.34a±0.09	0.291	*0.884
2	2.61c±1.17	2.53c±0.09	2.15d±0.05	3.68a±0.09	3.16b±0.14	0.104	*0.316
3	2.82b±0.03	3.06a±0.06	2.80b±0.03	2.95a±0.03	2.93a±0.04	0.044	*0.133
4	5.06a±0.12	3.74d±0.07	4.31c±0.11	4.06c±0.05	4.73b±0.10	0.098	*0.297
5	5.01b±0.01	4.96b±0.10	4.80b±0.07	6.10a±0.09	6.31a±0.15	0.098	*0.299
6	4.04d±0.02	5.42b±0.09	4.74c±0.03	5.14b±0.11	6.87a±0.17	0.105	*0.318
7	2.52c±0.02	2.70b±0.01	2.64b±0.01	3.11a±0.03	3.03a±0.03	0.027	*0.082
8	5.71a±0.08	5.13c±0.06	5.43b±0.05	5.75a±0.05	5.65a±0.08	0.069	*0.21
Overall	3.85b±0.02	3.91b±0.01	3.81b±0.02	4.31a±0.01	4.46a±0.01	0.011	*0.032

The effect of phytase supplementation on weekly and cumulative feed conversion ratio (FCR) in Pratapdhan
* $p < 0.05$ Means bearing different letters in a row differ significantly.

The fourth and fifth week's showed elevated FCR values across all treatments, the mean value of FCR in 4th week of age were 5.06 ± 0.12 , 3.74 ± 0.07 , 4.31 ± 0.11 , 4.06 ± 0.05 and 4.73 ± 0.10 in T₁, T₂, T₃, T₄ and T₅, respectively. Whereas, the mean value of FCR in 5th week of age were 5.01 ± 0.01 , 4.96 ± 0.10 , 4.80 ± 0.07 , 6.1 ± 0.09 and 6.31 ± 0.15 in T₁, T₂, T₃, T₄ and week of age were T₅, respectively. At 4th week, the mean FCR values were significantly highest in T₁ followed by T₅, T₃, T₄ and lowest in T₂. While the mean FCR at 5 weeks were significantly highest in T₅ followed by T₄, T₁, T₂ and lowest in T₃. Higher FCR values suggests as birds grow older their maintenance requirement increases resulting poor feed efficiency. Nevertheless, T₂ and T₃ consistently exhibited better FCR at 4th and 5th week respectively compared to T₁, T₄ and T₅. Notably, poorest feed efficiency was observed in T₄ and T₅ during the fifth week. During the sixth week, the mean value of FCR were 4.04 ± 0.02 , 5.42 ± 0.09 , 4.74 ± 0.03 , 5.14 ± 0.11 and 6.87 ± 0.17 in T₁, T₂, T₃, T₄ and T₅, respectively and T₁ demonstrated the best FCR, followed by T₃. However, FCR utilization. The seventh week showed an improvement in feed conversion across treatments, where the mean value of FCR were 2.52 ± 0.02 , 2.70 ± 0.01 , 2.64 ± 0.01 , 3.11 ± 0.03 and 3.03 ± 0.03 in T₁, T₂, T₃, T₄ and T₅, respectively. The mean FCR values at 7th week were significantly highest in T₄ and T₅ followed by T₂ and T₃ and lowest in T₁. However, the differences in FCR between T₄ and T₅ and T₂ and T₃ were found to be statistically non-significant. In the eighth week, the mean values of FCR were 5.71 ± 0.08 , 5.13 ± 0.06 , 5.43 ± 0.05 , 5.75 ± 0.05 and 5.65 ± 0.08 in T₁, T₂, T₃, T₄ and T₅, respectively. The mean FCR values at 8th week were significantly higher in T₄, T₁ and T₅ as compared to T₃ and T₂. However, the difference amongst T₁, T₄ and T₅ remained statistically non-significant. The trend of superior performance by T₃ continued, though all groups recorded relatively higher FCRs due to slowing growth rates and increased maintenance needs. T₁, T₄ and T₅ had the highest values, further emphasizing the relative inefficiency of these regimens during the finishing period which may be attributed to no phytase and lowered energy content in the diet. The overall FCR for the entire 8-week with the mean value of 3.85 ± 0.02 , 3.91 ± 0.01 , 3.81 ± 0.02 , 4.31 ± 0.01 and 4.46 ± 0.01 in T₁, T₂, T₃, T₄ and T₅, respectively and experimental period was significantly ($p < 0.05$) lowest in T₃, indicating superior feed efficiency, followed closely by T₁ and T₂. T₄ and had significantly poorer FCRs, suggesting that these combinations were less favorable for economic and biological feed utilization.

These studies are strongly in agreement with the findings of Poernama *et al.* (2021) [4], Anayaegbu *et al.* (2021) [5], Ali (2021) and de Franca *et al.* (2023) [7].

Conclusion

The results of the experiment concluded that the total feed intake was significantly highest ($p < 0.05$) in T₂ (2447.99 ± 4.10 g) as compared to T₅ (2443.17 ± 4.77 g), and T₃ (2439.72 ± 3.58 g) and lowest in T₄ (2341.17 ± 5.09 g) and T₁ (2326.88 ± 4.14 g). The supplementation of phytase enzyme significantly reduced ($p < 0.05$) FCR in T₃ (3.81 ± 0.01) as compared to other treatment groups.

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